

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF A RHETORICAL SENTENCE IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the psycholinguistic study of the concept of linguistic consciousness, the formation of psycholinguistics as an object, its founders, the results of the analysis of concepts and units uniting around linguistic consciousness in the field of psycholinguistics and linguistics.

Linguistic consciousness is a cognitive linguistic category that expresses the process of perception and understanding of the world by a representative of a certain language through lexical and grammatical units. According to T.N. Ushakova, the term "linguistic consciousness" is a combination of words that express separate, but interconnected concepts from the fields of psychology and linguistics and unites them.

In our opinion, such a combination of compatible concepts should be considered a sign of development. The reason for our conclusion is that we can observe their mutual correspondence in the constant movement of connection. Indeed, the use of linguistic units in speech by a person to express a thought is a process that arises as a reflection of his spiritual world. Undoubtedly, this is the essence of the concepts of language and speech.

"In the first half of the 20th century, the center of linguistics considered language as a system, and in literary studies - literature as a field of art, while by the end of the century, the category of homo loquens was present in both centers of science." Only in the first case, representatives of a high-level dialogue in the form of a two-way "speaker - listener" are implied, while in the second case, there are parties performing separate functions as "author - reader". In accordance with the development of the social environment, the ground was created for the emergence of new types of communicative activity through language, such as "Journalist - Reader", "Advertiser - Advertising Consumer", "Public Relations Specialist - Public" and other modifications of traditional dialogue.

Every person who uses language seeks to interest other people in his speech, therefore he relies on the means of expressing implicit or hidden meaning, which is characteristic of all oratorical methods, in particular, metaphor, epithet, comparison, metonymy, repetition, rhetorical question, omission of words, and other means. Hidden meanings in speech are based on the speaker's knowledge of the surrounding world, the characteristics of objects and

events. The personality of the speaker is nationally and culturally specific. When communicating with other people, the speaker most often refers to such basic concepts as "happiness", "money", "peace", "truth", "fate", "family", "homeland". National specificity lies in the fact that although the meaning of a particular word arises in connection with a certain situation, the metaphorical or metonymic meaning may arise in connection with a completely different concept. The hidden meaning of each word, changing its conceptual meaning, arises from the speaker's worldview in understanding the world, people, the surrounding reality, political processes in the world, etc.

It is recognized that a person's activities and actions depend to a certain extent on his knowledge and imagination. It should be borne in mind that his thoughts may not be fully expressed in human speech, since the process of communication involves the participation of the speaker as well as the listener.

There is an ancient tradition in linguistics that considers the function of language to be the representation of elements of the external world through linguistic units. From this point of view, situations can be divided into a number of parts that correspond to a certain linguistic unit.

A specific interpretation of reality, along with the representation of certain elements in a visually perceived situation, also includes signs outside our field of vision. In other words, within the framework of the topic under consideration, the subject is often the leading participant. The term "language carrier", which has been actively used in linguistics for the past thirty years, is closely related to the term "language representation of the world" as a central part of psycholinguistics. This concept, which has a long history and dates back to Wilhelm von Humboldt, was developed in the works of leading foreign and Russian linguists of the 20th century, and on the eve of the 21st century, interest in this problem is growing again. Each individual language, according to W. von Humboldt, has a unique structure, an "internal form" formed due to the "specificity of the national spirit", and is primarily a means of expressing the collective consciousness of the people through phraseological units and proverbs.

Each individual language interprets the world from the point of view of national culture. Although the term "language bearer" itself implies that in the self-understanding of this person certain ideas about some fundamental, most important features of understanding the world that are inherent in each linguistic unit are directly reflected, we can still talk about the specific features of the world in a particular region and ideas about the place of man in them. The term "language bearer" itself is directly related to the role of the human factor in language, which arose due to the anthropocentric approach to language, and reflects the entire cognitive activity of a person, as well as his attitude to the surrounding natural world, social values, other people and himself. Each individual language creates many other worlds that differ from reality. The consciousness of the language bearer is determined by imagination, at the same time, speech combines the real and imaginary worlds, possible and unimaginable situations. Linguistics Most of the knowledge about the world is formed due to language, but if it interpreted the world from a supernatural point of view, then over time, misunderstandings about the specific features of the world would increase between different peoples. However, this should not be expected, because, despite the existence of different languages and cultures, over time, due to intercultural contacts, it is necessary to master not

only vocabulary, but also phraseology in harmonizing knowledge about the world.

Linguistic study is one of the tasks of cognitive linguistics, which includes the study of cognitive problems and their reflection in language, the concept of language as a set of objective expressions reflecting the concentration of experience of a particular language community, expressed in language by its speaker as a carrier of certain ideas about the world. The similarities and differences of the world's languages should be studied within the framework of research on the hypothesis of linguistic consciousness.

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